

Quarks Masses Mixing – Mixing angles

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Abstract:

The following is a mathematical idea regarding the enigma of quark mixing. By manipulation of the first and second generation of quarks, it is possible to reach the total mass of the third. Since the masses could vary, there could be correction angles to the equation, i.e. mixing angles. Analysis of that idea suggest 11.5 degrees to be one of those correction angles.

Introduction

Take the masses of all the generations and combine them:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} [1.9] & [1320] & [172,760] \\ [4.4] & [87] & [4240] \end{array}$$

$$1.9 + 4.4 = 6.3 \quad (1)$$

$$1320 + 87 = 1407 \quad (2)$$

$$172,760 + 4240 = 177000 \quad (3)$$

The idea by Quark mixture we mean multiplication of masses of the first and second to Yield the total mass of third, times a scalar. Therefore, a total mass of the first family multiplied by the total mass of the second family, both multiplied by a scalar, will yield the total mass of The Third. We can proof that is the almost case exactly for the values of the masses above:

$$6.3 * 1407 = 8864.1$$

$$\frac{177,000}{8864.1} = 19.96$$

If we can allow a slight variation of the first masses to be 6.29 Mev and not 6.3, it will be

$$6.29 * 1407 = 8850$$

$$\frac{177,000}{8850} = 20 \quad (4)$$

Therefore, just a slight variation of 0.01 Mev and we have a beautiful number and a way to combine the total mass of the first and the second, mix them And multiply by the scalar, to reach the total mass of the third. Reader should argue that it could be just a coincidence, a choice of certain values to yield the scalar and he might be right as the masses are not measured or known as exact, they could divert.

Assuming the mixing will accrue at scalar numbers only, we can build correction angles to ensure the scalar number will hold. So if the masses of the first divert or measured at a higher value that 6.29, there will be a correction angle to retain the same scalar we obtained. The correction angles could have more than one value and they can be Positive or negative. Take the mass of the up quark to be average between 1.9 to 2.2 Mev, which is 2.05 Mev.

$$\frac{1.9 + 2.2}{2} = 2.05 \text{ Mev}$$

$$2.05 + 4.4 = 6.45 \text{ Mev}$$

$$6.45 * 1407 = 9075.15$$

$$\frac{177,000}{9075.15} = 19.503$$

The correction angle to reach desired number would be:

$$19.503 + \cos(11.5) \approx 20 \quad (5)$$

There could be many more, the correction angles are not limited in number and depend Upon the masses values taken of the first, second, and the third as well. The idea behind Stay the same. The correction angle will be added to yield a scalar multiple.

$$20 * (TotalMass(1) * TotalMass(2)) = TotalMass(3) \quad (6)$$

Among all the topics can be answered by the 8-theory, and there has been many, the question of Quark mixing seems to be among the hardest ones. This part is not a proof of any sort But a mathematical idea, the reader should rightfully argue and doubt it. One was trying to reason in the simplest and most elegant way, the weird phenomenon Of Quark mixing. Whether it makes sense or not, readers should decide after analyzing the Paper.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)